

STUDY OF INCOME GENERATION AND REPAYMENT CAPACITY OF FARMERS WITH THEIR SOCIO – ECONOMIC STATUS IN CUTTACK DISTRICT OF ODISHA.

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(MS Received: 18.05.2023; MS Revised:22.06.2023; MS Accepted:23.06.2023)

MS 3053

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS,)

Abstract

India and farming go hand in hand because the foundation of our economy is farming and the cooperative movement (1904) has laid the path of development of the farmers and the economy of India. As much as 76% of the total population of Odisha is engaged in agricultural activities. And as per the ongoing surveys India is going to be the most populated country in the world surpassing China by the next census. That means attracting people to the agriculture sector is the only sustainable way of living. Co-operative banks are the best suited banks for the farmers and for the development of agriculture. Odisha and specially the coastal belt area like Cuttack is very prone to the natural calamities, government helps the farmers about their loans and repayment through the bank and this helps in the growth of socio – economic status of the people. It also shows the improvement in education level, employment situation, income repayment of the people.

Keywords: co-operative bank, co-operative movement, category, natural calamities, socio economic, employment, income

Introduction

An important segment of the organized sector of the Indian banking system is represented by a group of financial institutions collectively called co-operative banks. They are so called because they have been organized under the provisions of the co-operative society's law of the states. Under the law, the co-operative societies may be organized for credit or for other (non-credit) purposes. Co-operative banks in India are providing general banking services to the general people. Two types of co-operative banks are working in India. Rural co-operative banks work mostly in rural areas and urban co-operative banks are working in urban areas. Rural co-operative banks are further sub-divided into state co-operative banks and district co-operative banks. All co-operative banks are registered under the state co-operative societies act. Cooperative banks run with the motto of "no profit, no loss". India and farming go hand in hand because the foundation of our economy is farming and the cooperative movement (1904) has laid the path of development of the farmers and the economy of India. As much as 76% of the total population of Odisha is engaged in agricultural activities. And as per the ongoing surveys, India is going to be the most populated country in the world surpassing China by the next census whereas India is the seventh-largest country by area. That means attracting people to the agriculture sector is the only sustainable way of living. In India, about 51.09% of the land is under cultivation, 21.81% under forest, and 3.92% under pasture. To feed so many mouths from this much of agriculture land is a tough task unless quality use of those lands are done. Unless we have to depend upon others for our own daily needs. And import is the worst enemy of any country's economy. So getting more people involved in the agriculture sector is our one and only way of producing the require amount of product. Co-operative banks are the best suited banks for the farmers and for the development of agriculture. Odisha and specially the coastal belt area like Cuttack is very prone to the natural calamities, government helps the farmers about their loans and repayment through the bank and this helps in the growth of socio – economic status of the people. It also shows the improvement in education level, employment situation, income repayment of the people.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where, O_{ij} = Observed frequency of the cell in (i)th row and (j)th column.
 E_{ij} = Expected frequency of the cell in (i)th row and (j)th column

Materials and Methods

Stratified multistage sampling procedure was adopted for selection of sample and data collection for the present study. Odisha state contains 30 districts. Keeping the limitation of resource only 1 district of Odisha is selected. It was arranged alphabetically and out of which **Cuttack** district was selected purposely. A complete list of blocks was taken from the district headquarter of Cuttack. The blocks were arranged alphabetically and out of the 14 blocks, **Banki** block was selected purposely. A complete list of all the main and sub-branches of the Co-operative banks present in the Banki block were collected. Out of the 11 branches, Banki main branch was selected purposely. A complete list of villages was taken from the B.D.O. office. Out of total, 5% villages were selected randomly. A complete list of the respondents was taken from the bank. They were arranged according to their farm holdings in ascending order. Out of the total 10% respondents were selected randomly. Respondents have been chosen randomly with subject to their availability and coordination during the time of study. The primary data have been collected by survey method through personal interviews and questioners on well-structured schedule. Secondary was be collected from books, journals, report and records of the district head office and Govt Official Sites and NGOs and SHG groups.

Analytical tools

To segregate the collected data from farmers into homogeneous groups to enable comparison. For this, tabulation, graphical representation and percentage is going to be used.

1. Frequency: It is used to know the distribution pattern of respondents variable wise and to categorize the problems perceived by respondents in order of importance.
2. Percentage: It refers to a special kind of ratio which is used in making comparison between two or more series of data.

$$\text{Percentage} = (X \div Y) * 100$$

Where, X= No. of respondents filling for the same category

Y= Total no of respondents

3. Chi-square test: It is going to be used to identify the association between some factors of socio-economic condition of adopted and non-adopted farmers.

Results and Discussion**1. Socio-economic status of the respondents****Table.1.1. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their gender**

S. No.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Male	102	85.00	
2	Female	18	15.00	
Total		120	100.00	

Table 1.1 shows that highest percentage of farmers are male (85%) and female (15%). Chi square test value signifies that there is no significance between the gender of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.2. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their age

S. No.	Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Below 25 years	6	5.00	
2	25- 50 years	61	50.83	
3	50- 65 years	41	34.17	
4	More than 65 years	12	10.00	
Total		120	100.00	3.29

Table 1.2 shows that highest percentage of farmers are 25-50 years old (50.83%), then 50-65 years old (34.17%), more than 65 years are 10% and below 25 years are 5%. Chi square test value signifies that there is no significance between the age of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.3. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their education

S. No.	Education	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Less than HSC	25	20.83	
2	HSC	44	36.67	
3	Graduate	39	32.50	
4	Post-graduate	12	10.00	
Total		120	100.00	16.47

Table 1.3 shows that highest percentage of farmers are HSC (36.67%), then Graduates (32.50%), less than HSC are 20.83% and post graduates are 10%. Chi square test value signifies that there is significance between the qualification of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.4. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their occupation

S. No.	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Student	9	7.50	
2	Farmer	63	52.50	
3	Employee	26	21.67	
4	Business	16	13.33	
5	Retired	6	5.00	
Total		120	100.00	7.25

Table 1.4 shows that highest percentage of farmers are 52.50%, then Employee (21.67%), Business men are 13.33%, students are 7.50% and Retired persons are 5%. Chi square test value signifies that there is no significance between the occupation of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.5. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their land holding

S. No.	Land holding	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Less than 1 ha	18	15.00	
2	1 – 2 ha	22	18.33	
3	2 – 4 ha	27	22.50	
4	4 – 10 ha	34	28.33	
5	More than 10 ha	19	15.83	
Total		120	100.00	29.23

Table 1.5 shows that highest percentage of farmers are medium 28.33%, then semi-medium (22.50%), small farmers are 18.33%, large farmers are 15.83% and marginal farmers are 15%. Chi square test value signifies that there is significance between the land holding of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.6. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their family size

S. No.	Size of family	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value
1	Small family	68	56.67	
2	Medium family	27	22.50	
3	Large family	25	20.83	
Total		120	100.00	4.51

Table 1.6 shows that highest percentage of farmers have small family 56.67%, then medium family 22.50%, and large family 20.83%. Chi square test value signifies that there is no significance between the family size of farmers and access to bank or loan.

Table.1.7. Distribution of beneficiaries based on their place of residence

S. No.	Place of residence	Frequency	Percentage
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1	Urban	68	56.67	Chi square test value 4.51
2	Semi-urban	27	22.50	
3	Rural	25	20.83	
Total		19	100.00	

Table 1.7 shows that highest percentage of farmers are from urban area 56.67%, then semi urban 22.50%, and rural area 20.83%. Chi square test value signifies that there is no significance between the place of residence of farmers and access to bank or loan.

2. Income generation

Table.2 Distribution of beneficiaries based on their annual income

S. No.	Annual income	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value 24.85
1	Below 3 lakhs	56	46.67	
2	3-10 lakhs	46	38.33	
3	More than 10 lakhs	18	15.00	
Total		120	100.00	

Table 2. shows that highest percentage of farmers income is below 3 lakhs 46.67%, then 3 – 10 lakhs 38.33%, and more than 10 lakhs 15%. Chi square test value signifies that there is significance between the annual income of farmers and access to bank or loan.

3.Repayment capacity

Table.3 Distribution of beneficiaries based on their income generation and repayment capacity

S. No.	Before or after loan	Average Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage	Chi square test value 8.52
1	Before loan	Below 3 lakhs	73	60.83	
		3-10 lakhs	41	34.17	
		More than 10 lakhs	6	5.00	
2	After loan	Below 3 lakhs	56	46.67	
		3-10 lakhs	46	38.33	
		More than 10 lakhs	18	15.00	

Table 3. shows that there was significant increase in their income and thus their repayment capacity has increased also. Before loan there were 60.83% farmers below 3 lakhs, 34.17% in 3-10 lakhs category and 5% in more than 10 lakhs category. Whereas after loan there were 46.67% below 3 lakhs, 38.33% in 3-10 lakhs and 15% in more than 10 lakhs category. Chi square test value signifies that there is significance between the annual income of farmers and their repayment capacity before and after loan.

Conclusion

There were more male farmers than female. Middle-aged farmers were more compared to the other age groups. Employment condition in agriculture is more compared to other sectors. Income generation capacity of farmers has developed after loan from bank and so as their repayment capacity. Land holding and annual income of farmers play a major role in financing of agriculture from bank or getting any type of loan for agriculture or allied sector and overall socio-economic status of the farmers and their family.

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